

DIVINFOOD

Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based food

Deliverable D1.4

Typology of short and mid-tier chains valuing biodiversity, including SMART indexes of agrobiodiversity use in marketing and data

Additional material to Appendix 3

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Public – PU	x
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RÉPUBLIQUE
FRANÇAISE

*Liberté
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INRAE

Valuing food products made from neglected and under-utilised crops

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

1 Introduction

DIVINFOOD aims at developing food chains valuing agrobiodiversity and procuring plant-based food that are good for health, farmers and the planet. To achieve this, a survey is being conducted with all initiatives (companies, farmers, shops, associations, organisations, cooperatives...) that sell or promote neglected and underutilised legumes and cereals (NUCs) in 7 European countries (Denmark, France, Hungary, Italy, Portugal, Sweden and Switzerland), such as legumes or cereals from old, local or indigenous varieties. This survey is managed by INRAE and the information will be processed by INRAE.

The decision to take part in this survey is voluntary and should take a maximum of 15 minutes.

The information that you will provide by completing this questionnaire will only be used in a secured way by INRAE and only for the research objectives explained above. In particular, no use for commercial purpose will be made with your information, and your information will not be shared with other parties. Your information will be stored in the best security and confidentiality conditions during the duration of the research project and up to five years after the project has ended, that is to say until 28 February 2027. After this date, the information will be archived according to the French heritage code.

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You are free to accept or refuse to complete this survey. If you accept, you have the right to withdraw from the questionnaire at any moment without providing a reason for it.

2 Profile of the initiative

* 2.1 Name of your initiative/business/organization

(hereafter referred to as initiative)

* 2.2 Year founded

Only values between 1500 and 2024 are allowed

* 2.3 Country

- Denmark
- France
- Hungary
- Italy
- Portugal
- Sweden
- Switzerland
- Other

* 2.4 Please specify:

* 2.5 City

* 2.6 How many other locations do you have?

- 0
- 1
- 2
- 3-5
- 6-9
- >10

* 2.7 How would you describe your commercial activities?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Inputs production
- Food production
- Agro-tourism

- Wholesaling
- Processing
- Transporting or delivery service
- Advertising/marketing/promotion/valorisation
- Education
- Food service
- Food storage/warehouse
- Selling food/retail
- Certifying
- Public regulator
- Blogging
- Journalism
- Research
- Other

* 2.8 Please specify your other activities:

* 2.9 Please specify:

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Supermarket/hypermarket
(incl. delivery, pick-up services)
- Grocery
- Hard-discount shop
- Specialty shop
(e.g. bakery, butchery, fruit and vegetable shop...)
- Frozen food shop
- Organic shop
- Open-air market/farmers' market
- On-farm selling point
- Collective farmers' shop
(incl. drive pick-up services)
- Community-Supported Agriculture
- Online platform selling local and/or organic food
- Online platform for the sale of ready-to-use meal and/or vegetable boxes
- Other

* 2.10 Please specify:

* 2.11 Can you describe briefly your initiative?

(main and complementary activities, products and services offered, objectives, visions, principles and missions that guide your initiative...)

5000 character(s) maximum

* 2.12 Does your initiative have a social mission?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

* 2.13 Are these missions intended to fight:

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Obesity
- Malnutrition
- Undernutrition
- Gluten intolerance
- Overconsumption of meat
- Food fraud
- Food insecurity
- Unsustainable agricultural, production or distribution practices
- Environmental degradation
- Climate change
- Biodiversity decline
- Unfair global trade
- Unfair remuneration of producers
- Other

* 2.14 Please specify:

3 Plant-based foods and NUCs

* 3.1 What foods does your initiative deal with?

(i.e. that you produce, process, sell, promote/value and/or certify, depending on your initiative's activities)

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Legumes/legume-based products
- Cereals/cereal-based products
- Vegetables/vegetables-based products
- Fruits/fruit-based products
- Nuts/nut-based products
- Seeds/seed-based products
- Other

* 3.2 Please specify:

* 3.3 Among the foods covered by your initiative, do you consider any to be neglected or underutilized crops (NUCs, e.g. legumes or cereals from old, local or indigenous varieties)?

NUCs are “domesticated plant species that have been cultivated or consumed as food throughout human history, but have been reduced in importance over time...with many of them actually disappearing” (da Silva J., FAO, 2012)

- Yes
 No
 I don't know

* 3.4 Which ones?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Legumes/Legume-based products
 Cereals/Cereal-based products
 Vegetables/vegetable-based products
 Fruits/fruit-based products
 Nuts/nut-based products
 Seeds/seed-based products
 Other

* 3.5 Please specify the other foods you consider as being NUCs:

* 3.6 Please specify the variety of legumes that you consider as being NUCs:

* 3.7 Please specify the variety of cereals that you consider as being NUCs:

* 3.8 Please specify the variety of vegetables that you consider as being NUCs:

* 3.9 Please specify the variety of fruits that you consider as being NUCs:

* 3.10 Please specify the variety of nuts that you consider as being NUCs:

3.11 Please specify the variety of seeds that you consider as being NUCs:

*

* 3.12 Please specify the variety of other foods that you consider as being NUCs:

* 3.13 Why do you think these are NUCs?

5000 character(s) maximum

* 3.14 What percentage of your activity is related to NUCs?

- <5%
- 5 - 25%
- 26 - 50%
- 51 - 75%
- 76 - 95%
- >95%

* 3.15 What is the origin of the NUCs that your initiative deals with?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Same municipality
- Same region
- Same country
- Same continent
- Outside Europe
- I don't know
- My initiative is not concerned with NUCs sourcing/origin issues

* 3.16 Do the NUCs that your initiative deals with come directly from producers?

- Yes
- No
- Both directly and indirectly
- I am the producer of the NUCs
- I don't know

* 3.17 If directly, what type of contracts are established with producers for the supply of NUCs?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- 1 time sale
- Auction
- Annual contract
- Long-term contract (pluriannual)
- Other

I don't know

* 3.18 Please specify:

* 3.19 If indirectly, how many intermediaries (excluding the producer and your initiative) are involved for the supply of NUCs?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- 1
 2
 3
 4
 5
 >5
 I don't know

* 3.20 Does your initiative sell NUCs/NUC-based products directly to consumers? (*i.e., no intermediaries between your initiative and the consumer*)

- Yes, directly to consumers only
 Yes, both directly and indirectly to consumers
 No, indirect sales only
 My initiative is not concerned by the sale of food.

* 3.21 Can you estimate the share (%) of the NUCs/NUC-based products of your initiative that is sold directly to consumers?

Only values between 0 and 100 are allowed

* 3.22 How would you describe the consumers of the NUCs/NUC-based products you sell?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- One-off consumers (single purchase)
 Repeat consumers (once monthly)
 Frequent consumers (once a week or more)
 Members of a loyalty program
 I don't know

* 3.23 How many intermediaries are there between your initiative and the consumer ?
(for your indirect sales of NUCs/NUC-based products)

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- 1
 2
 3
 4
 5
 >5

I don't know

4 Digital tools in your initiative and communication

* 4.1 Do you use online platforms?

(e.g. a website, social media such as Facebook, video channels such as YouTube)

- Yes
 No
 I don't know

* 4.2 Which platforms do you use?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Your own website
 Another company's website
(e.g., Amazon, eBay, Ali Baba)
 Facebook
 X - Twitter
 Instagram
 YouTube
 Whatsapp
 TikTok
 Snapchat
 Pinterest
 LinkedIn
 Other

* 4.3 Please specify:

* 4.4 For which of the following purposes?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Marketing/selling purposes
(promoting your initiative, increasing sales, managing internet sales, promoting products...)
 Information/content sharing
(e.g. farming practices, origin of products...)
 Create/maintain a community around your initiative
 Activism
 Other

* 4.5 Please specify:

* 4.6 Do you rely on other means of communication?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Word of mouth
- Labels (e.g. organic logo...)
- Brochures/flyers
- Posters
- Workshops/trainings
- Radio
- TV
- Sales point display
- Other
- None of the above

* 4.7 Please specify:

* 4.8 Do you actively promote the consumption of NUCs/NUC-based products?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

* 4.9 Which of the following qualities of NUCs/NUC-based products do you promote?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Health and nutrition
(e.g. rich in iron, fiber and protein)
- Environmental/landscape preservation
- (Agro)biodiversity conservation/restoration
- Culture and gastronomy (preserving identity and heritage)
- Affordable price
- Good value for money
- Medical properties (e.g. anti-stress properties)
- Diet transition towards vegan/vegetarian
- Promoting local agriculture
- Other

* 4.10 Please specify:

* 4.11 What communication channels do you use to promote NUCs/NUC-based products?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Online platforms
(e.g. a website, social media such as Facebook, video channels such as YouTube...)
- Word of mouth
- Labels (e.g. organic logo...)
- Brochures/flyers
- Posters
- Workshops/trainings

- Radio
- TV
- Sales point display
- Other

* 4.12 What kind of sales point display are you implementing to promote NUCs/NUC-based products?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Discount campaign
- Discount coupons
- Putting NUCs at the top of gondola shelves or highlighting them on displays
- Volume discount
(e.g. buy two, get one free)
- Loyalty promotion
- Bundle
(e.g., sets of other products in association with NUCs)
- Tasting campaign
- Other

* 4.13 Please specify:

* 4.14 Please specify your other communication channels:

* 4.15 Do you do any of the following to promote NUCs/NUC-based products?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Cooking demonstrations
- Talks/speeches
- Teaching
- Campaigning
- Activism
- Other
- None of the above

* 4.16 Please specify:

* 4.17 Where do you do these activities?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- On social media
- In your main location
- In your other locations
- In a public venue
(e.g., community hall, cultural centre)

- In local events
- In regional events
- In national events
- In international events
- Other

* 4.18 Please specify:

* 4.19 Do you solicit feedback from consumers?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

* 4.20 What communication channels do you use to solicit feedback from consumers?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Your own website
(e.g., via contact forms)
- Another company's website
(e.g., Yelp, Pinterest, Feedback Forum)
- E-mail
- Through interaction on social media
(e.g., comments or private messages on Facebook...)
- Through direct exchanges with the customer
(at the point of sale, delivery, during a visit to the farm...)
- Other

* 4.21 Please specify:

5 Production, quality and prices

* 5.1 Do you guarantee the quality of the NUCs/NUC-based products you sell or promote?

- Yes
- No

* 5.2 How is this quality of NUCs/NUC-based products guaranteed?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Third party certification
- Participatory guarantee system (PGS)
- Social control
- Consumer feedback
- Business-to-business (B2B) verification
- Self-declaration

Other

* 5.3 Please specify:

* 5.4 What are these guaranteed qualities of NUCs/NUC-based products?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Taste
- Size
- Color
- Place/origin
- Organic
- Tradition
- Religion
- Vegan
- Easy to cook/process
- Known recipes
- Nutrition benefits
- Weight loss
- Medical properties
- Psychedelic properties
- Ecosystem services
(e.g. nitrogen fixation, pollination, intercropping)
- Other

* 5.5 Please specify:

* 5.6 Do you provide information to consumers about how NUCs are grown?

- Yes
- No

* 5.7 What do you typically say?

5000 character(s) maximum

* 5.8 How do you share this information?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Online platforms
(e.g. a website, social media such as Facebook, video channels such as YouTube...)
- Word of mouth

- Labels
(e.g., organic logo)
- Brochures/flyers
- Posters
- Workshops/trainings
- Radio
- TV
- Sales point display
- Other

* 5.9 Please specify:

* 5.10 What benefit(s) does the sale or promotion of NUCs/NUC-based products provide for your initiative?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Cultural
- Social
- Economic
- Environmental
- Political
- Other
- Provide(s) no additional benefits

* 5.11 Please specify (cultural benefits):

* 5.12 Please specify (social benefits):

* 5.13 Please specify (economic benefits):

* 5.14 Please specify (environmental benefits):

* 5.15 Please specify (political benefits):

* 5.16 Please specify (other benefits):

* 5.17 Do you sell or promote NUCs/NUC-based products only when they are in season?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

* 5.18 Please explain:

* 5.19 How do the consumer prices of NUCs/NUC-based products compare to similar non-NUC products?

- Higher
- The same
- Lower

* 5.20 How do the profit margins you make for NUCs/NUC-based products compare to similar non-NUC products?

- Higher
- The same
- Lower

6 Competition, demand and challenges

* 6.1 Do you face competition in the sales or promotion of NUCs/NUC-based products?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't know

* 6.2 How high is the competition?

- High
- Medium
- Low

* 6.3 What are the main challenges of producing NUCs?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Unavailability of seeds
- Unfavorable agronomic conditions
- Lack of organic inputs
- Lack of integrated cropping systems
- Lack of markets
- Other
- No specific NUCs production challenges

* 6.4 Please specify (other producing challenges):

* 6.5 How can we overcome the production challenges you identified?

* 6.6 What are the main challenges of processing NUCs?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Organoleptic qualities
- Physical qualities
- Lack of tasty recipes
- Too much competition among products
- Insufficient supply
- Insufficient demand
- Other
- No specific NUCs processing challenges

* 6.7 Please specify (other processing challenges):

* 6.8 How can we overcome the processing challenges you identified?

* 6.9 What are the main challenges of selling NUCs/NUC-based products?

Minimum 1 selection(s)

- Organoleptic qualities
- Physical qualities
- Lack of tasty recipes
- Too much competition among products
- Limited product range
- Lack of consumer awareness
- Lack of consumer knowledge of how to cook them
- Other
- No specific NUCs/NUC based-products selling challenges

* 6.10 Please specify (other selling challenges):

* 6.11 How can we overcome the selling challenges you identified?

7 Thank you!

* 7.1 Would you be interested in participating in the DIVINFOOD project?

Yes

No

7.2 Email:

7.3 Comments:

2000 character(s) maximum